

Bidentate Pyrimidine-2-thiols as Spectrophotometric Reagents for Palladium and Osmium—Determination in Alloys, Minerals and Catalysts

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1-Pyridyl and 1-(4'-phenylthiazolyl)-4,4,6-trimethyl-1*H*,4*H*-pyrimidine-2-thiol (abbreviated as PyTPT and PhTPT, respectively) have been synthesised and studied for the photometric determination of palladium and osmium. The reagents are highly selective as other transition and platinum group metals do not interfere. Optimum conditions for both these determinations have been established. The methods have been employed for the determination of palladium and osmium contents of various alloys, minerals and catalysts.

MONODENTATE pyrimidine-2-thiols are highly selective spectrophotometric reagents¹ for palladium and osmium but lack in sensitivity. Similar thiols having bidentate nature, however, have not been explored. The chelation due to bidentate character may possibly increase the sensitivity which is not high with monodentate ones. Two such thiols, 1-pyridyl and 1-(4'-phenylthiazolyl)-4,4,6-trimethyl-1*H*,4*H*-pyrimidine-2-thiol (abbreviated as PyTPT and PhTPT, respectively) were therefore, synthesised and investigated for the photometric determination of the two metals. Results presented in this paper reveal that better sensitivity as well as selectivity can be achieved with their use. Using these procedures the palladium and osmium contents of several alloys, catalysts and minerals are estimated successfully.

Experimental

Beckman DU-2, Unicam SP 500 and 600 spectrophotometers with 1.0 cm glass or quartz cells were used for measuring absorbance and a Beckman Expandomatic SS-2 pH-meter for pH measurement.

PyTPT and PhTPT were prepared by the method of Mathes² starting with 2-aminopyridine and 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, respectively. Their 0.01 M solutions were prepared in chloroform,

n-butanol and acetone. Standard solution of Pd²⁺ was prepared by dissolving PdCl₂ (Johnson Matthey, England) in 1.0 N HCl and standardised gravimetrically³. Solution of Os^{VIII} was obtained by dissolving OsO₄ in 0.1 N NaOH and standardised volumetrically⁴.

Results

Complexation of PyTPT: Colourless solution of PyTPT (λ_{max} 290 nm; 4.5×10^3 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) reacts with Pd²⁺ and Os^{VIII} instantaneously in hydrochloric acid medium forming 1:2 (metal to ligand ratio as determined by Job's method), n-butanol-extractable coloured complex. Adopting the following procedures, the two metals can be photometrically determined.

Determination of Pd with PyTPT: To a suitable aliquot of palladium solution containing 37.2 to 131.8 μ g of the metal was added 1.5 ml of 10 N hydrochloric acid. The solution was diluted to 10 ml and shaken for 5 min with 10 ml of 0.01 M PyTPT solution in n-butanol. The organic layer was removed and after centrifuging, its absorbance was measured at λ_{max} 430 nm (ϵ 5.2×10^3 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) against solvent blank. The metal content was deduced from a calibration curve.

A minimum of 20-fold molar excess of ligand over metal is required for full colour development. Beer's law is obeyed upto 17.8 ppm. Sandell's sensitivity to the reaction is 0.0204 μ g cm⁻². The colour remains stable for 12 h. The relative standard deviation for 10.7 ppm Pd determination has been found to be 0.8%. Other water immiscible solvents have also been tried for extraction but give lower absorbance values. Maximum extraction into n-butanol has been observed at acidity level 0.1 to 1.8 N (HCl).

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Effect of diverse ions has been investigated and the tolerance limits (ppm) in the determination of 10.7 ppm Pd are as follows. Fluoride, bromide and nitrate (7500); phosphate and borate (6000); acetate and oxalate (2500); citrate (1500), EDTA, sulphate and tartrate (900); nitrate, thiocyanate, sulphite and iodide (500); thiosulphate (60); Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} and Al^{III} (7000); Pb^{II} (2000); V^V , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} (1800); Fe^{II} and Sn^{II} (1000); Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} (6000); Pt^{IV} (4000); Au^{III} (100) and Bi^{III} , Ag^I and Fe^{II} (50). Since the Pd^{II} -PhTPT complex exhibits maximum absorbance in the acidity range 0.1-1.8 *N*, the interference of upto 5000 ppm osmium can be avoided if the determination is carried out at < 0.5 *N* acid concentration. Osmium does not form complex below an acidity of 0.5 *N*. Cyanide and thiourea interfere seriously.

Determination of Os with PyTPT : The procedure for osmium estimation is similar to that of palladium. The aliquot taken must contain 83 to 238 μg of the metal as Os^{VIII} . After the addition of HCl (0.8 to 1.5 ml of 10 *N*) and dilution to 10 ml, the solution is shaken with 10 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ PyTPT in *n*-butanol for 10 min. The absorbance of the non-aqueous layer is measured at 530 nm against solvent blank and the osmium content deduced from the calibration curve. A 25-fold molar excess of PyTPT over metal is required for maximum colour formation. Beer's law is followed upto 27.3 ppm. Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is $0.04 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The absorbance remains constant upto 12 h. For 19.02 ppm Os determination the relative standard deviation has been found to be 1.1%. Extraction into other organic solvents has been found lesser. The limits (ppm) upto which diverse ions are found tolerable in the determination of 10.02 ppm Os are as follows. Fluoride, bromide and nitrate (5000); sulphate and acetate (4000); phosphate, borate, oxalate and citrate (2000); tartrate and EDTA (1000); iodide (300); thiosulphate (150); nitrite (50); Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} (4500); Al^{III} , Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} (2000); Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} and V^V (1500); Sn^{II} (400); Hg^{II} (200), Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} (2000); Ir^{III} (1500); Pt^{IV} (400); Au^{III} (50); and Ag^I (20). Pd^{II} can be extracted beforehand at an acidity of 0.2-0.3 *N* (upto 400 ppm) since Os does not form complex at < 0.5 *N* acidity. Cyanide and thiourea interfere.

Reaction of PhTPT : PhTPT (λ_{max} 320 nm, ϵ $1.8 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) also forms 1 : 2 (metal to ligand ratio as determined by Job's method) complex with both the metal ions. Pd-complex (λ_{max} 340 nm, ϵ $2.5 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is chloroform-extractable and formed in acidic medium (maximum complexation in 1.0 to 2.5 *N* HCl). Os^{VIII} gives black opacity when treated with PhTPT in acidic medium but forms orange yellow complex (λ_{max} 400 nm, ϵ $2.0 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at pH 10-11.5. The latter species is non-extractable and has been studied in 50% acetone to keep the

ligand in solution. Stability of both these complexes has been found to be more than 12 h.

Procedure for determination of Pd with PhTPT : It is similar to that described under PyTPT except that the extraction has to be carried out with 10 ml of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ PhTPT from an acidic solution containing 10 to 33.3 μg of the metal. Chloroform has been found the most suitable extractant. The relative standard deviation for the method is of the order of 1%. At least 40-fold molar excess of ligand over metal is required for the full development of colour. Beer's law is obeyed upto 4.0 ppm and Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is $0.0042 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. In the determination of 2.66 ppm of palladium the following are the tolerance limits of various ions (ppm). Fluoride and bromide (8000); nitrate, phosphate and borate (5000); acetate, oxalate and tartrate (2000); citrate (1000); EDTA, sulphate and sulphite (500); thiosulphate and thiocyanate (100); iodide (20); Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} and Al^{III} (5000); Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} (3000); Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} (2500); Pb^{II} (2000); V^V and Mn^{II} (500); Hg^{II} (100); Fe^{II} (50); Ag^I (2); Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} (5000); Ru^{III} (400); and Pt^{IV} and Au^{III} (50). Bi^{III} , Os^{VIII} , cyanide and thiourea interfere seriously.

Procedure for Os determination with PhTPT : A suitable aliquot of Os^{VIII} solution (containing 15 to 42 μg of metal) was treated with 2 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ PhTPT in acetone and pH of the mixture was adjusted to 10.5. After making up the volume to 10 ml maintaining 50% acetone concentration, the absorbance was noted at 400 nm against the reagent blank. The metal content was read from pre-calibrated curve. For stable colour system a 35-fold molar excess of ligand over metal has to be maintained. The relative standard deviation for 4.75 ppm Os is $\sim 1.0\%$. Beer's law is followed upto 9.2 ppm and Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is $0.0091 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

The tolerance limits (ppm) of various ions in the determination of 4.75 ppm of osmium are as follows. Chloride and bromide (8000); iodide and nitrate (5000); thiosulphate, sulphite and sulphate (5000); tartrate (4000); citrate and oxalate (3000); fluoride and phosphate (2000); borate and acetate (1000); EDTA (400); nitrite (200); thiourea (100); cyanide (20); Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} (8000); Cu^{II} and Co^{II} (1000); Ni^{II} (2000); Al^{III} and Fe^{II} (500); Mn^{II} and Sn^{II} (400); Pb^{II} (200); Hg^{II} (25; 40, iodide); Ag^I (20; 50, chloride); Au^{III} (20); Pt^{IV} and Ir^{III} (500); Ru^{III} (400); and Rh^{III} (150). Palladium interferes. Wherever masking agents have been used, these have been mentioned in parentheses after the tolerance of the unmasked and masked ions.

Discussion

PyTPT, of course not much better in terms of sensitivity, has been found far superior in selectivity in comparison to monodentate pyrimidine-2-thiols¹.

TABLE 1—Pd AND Os DETERMINATION IN ALLOYS, MINERALS AND CATALYSTS

Sample	Pd %			Number of determination	Relative standard deviation (%)	
	Reported	Found			PyTPT	PhTPT
		PyTPT	PhTPT			
Jewellery alloy (45% Pd-4.5% Ru)	95	94.91	95.01	6	2.61	2.56
Stibiopalladinite	75	75.08	74.92	6	2.42	2.46
Jewellery alloy (50% Pd-50% Au)	50	50.08	50.04	6	1.98	2.09
Properzite mineral	6.7	6.60	6.74	6	1.44	1.50
Pd-asbestos catalyst	4.34	4.38	4.36	6	0.86	0.90
Pd-Al ₂ O ₃ catalyst	4.14	4.16	4.16	6	0.78	0.64
Pd-CaSO ₄ catalyst	5.91	5.88	5.95	6	0.81	0.76
Pd-BaSO ₄ catalyst	10.02	10.08	9.98	6	0.84	0.92
Pd-charcoal catalyst	9.01	9.00	8.94	6	0.76	1.0
Au-Pt-Pd (dental) alloy	0.16	0.164	0.167	6	1.08	0.82
Au-Pd (dental) alloy	2.26	2.25	2.27	6	0.66	0.71
Irido-osmium	30.10	30.21	*	6	1.01	—

* Determination not possible because Pd interferes.

Au⁺⁺⁺ is tolerable upto a good amount (50-times excess) with both the metals and they can be determined in presence of large excess of each other if acidity is properly selected. These are the only interference with monodentate reagents of this kind, which can be overcome with the use of PyTPT. Most probably the lesser sensitivity of PyTPT than PhTPT is due to the lower stability of its complexes, which results from the greater possible free rotation of pyridine ring about the single bond (connecting it with the pyrimidine ring) than of 4-phenylthiazolyl group. Moreover, rotation in the latter case brings another potent donor at the suitable position whereas this does not occur with PyTPT.

PhTPT cannot be used to determine Pd and Os in presence of each other. However, Au⁺⁺⁺ is again not tolerable to a good extent in Pd determination. The sensitivity can be much improved if it is used in place of monodentate ligands of this class. PyTPT and PhTPT both have distinct advantages of higher selectivity and rapid and simple

procedures free from stringent working conditions over the commonly used reagents for these metal ions^{5,6}. PhTPT is more sensitive in their comparison.

Determination of Pd and Os in alloys, catalysts and minerals: The samples were brought into solution by the procedures reported in literature^{5,6}. Pd and Os contents of these samples were determined by the above mentioned procedures. The results are recorded in Table 1.

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